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EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN pH AND THE COLOR OF RED CABBAGE EXTRACT UNDER RGB LED ILLUMINATION USING MACHINE LEARNING

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Abstract

Machine learning resources have become consolidated as relevant tools for analyzing multidimensional datasets, particularly in qualitative and quantitative studies of substances under different experimental conditions. In this work, we investigate the relationship between pH and the color of red cabbage extract using an accessible experimental setup composed of a plastic structure that aligns an RGB LED, a standard glass cuvette, and a smartphone camera. Each primary color of the LED was used separately to produce specific transmittance conditions, allowing the colorimetric variations of the extract to be recorded across pH levels ranging from 2.0 to 9.0. Based on independent repetitions for each combination of pH and illumination color, a dataset with more than one hundred samples and five features was obtained and analyzed using machine learning methods in both unsupervised (clustering) and supervised (regression) domains. The results indicated that samples illuminated by the green LED exhibited greater separation in HSV space, enabling the development of a more consistent predictive model for estimating pH from the color parameters. These findings reinforce the utility of low-cost experimental approaches combined with modern computational analysis for the quantitative investigation of natural indicators and for the construction of machine-learning-based predictive models.

Keywords: Chemistry; indicators; pH; machine learning; digital colorimetry.

1 INTRODUCTION

Natural acid-base indicators have received increasing attention in research aimed at low-cost solutions with lower environmental impact. Among these materials, red cabbage extract stands out for its marked color variation as a function of pH, wide availability, and applicability in different experimental scenarios (Amaral, 2023). However, the digital recording of these variations also depends on illumination conditions, since the light reflected or transmitted by the sample directly influences the obtained colorimetric response.

The integration of accessible materials, simple instrumental techniques, and modern numerical analysis methods allows for a more rigorous exploration of this system. The quantitative relationship between pH and the color of natural extracts (Wulan Hastuti, 2020), especially under controlled light sources, constitutes a relevant experimental problem that can benefit from the use of appropriate color spaces and data analysis algorithms.

In this work, we present an experimental setup designed to investigate how red cabbage extract responds to ten distinct pH levels when separately illuminated by the three colors of an RGB LED (Red, Green, Blue). The samples were recorded by a smartphone camera and the data structured in the HSV (Hue, Saturation, Value) space. From this dataset, we

applied different clustering and classification methods to compare the consistency of the images obtained under each illumination (Chioson, 2018). We also evaluated a supervised learning method with the aim of estimating the pH value from the records obtained with the green LED.

The proposal combines a low-cost experiment, based on easily obtainable materials such as red cabbage extract, RGB LED, and solutions prepared from bleach, with quantitative analysis procedures via machine learning. The use of simple reagents also allowed discussing relevant practical limitations, such as the distinction between color changes caused by pH variation and those resulting from oxidative processes. Based on these elements, the work developed around the following research question: How does the color of red cabbage extract, recorded under different illuminations (RGB LEDs), relate to the solution pH, and which illumination condition allows estimating pH with greater consistency?

The conceptual aspects underpinning this investigation, including the chemical behavior of anthocyanins, the color spaces used, and the application of machine learning techniques, are presented in Section 2.

2 THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

2.1 Anthocyanins, Red Cabbage Extract and Acid-Base Behavior

Anthocyanins are natural dyes present in flowers, fruits, and vegetables, expressing tones ranging from red to violet and blue, occurring in various species and plant parts (Amaral, 2023). Red cabbage extract (*Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata* f. *rubra*) has been widely presented in scientific articles, as well as proposed in educational activities, due to its efficiency as a natural acid-base indicator (Santos, 2013).

Red cabbage has a high content of anthocyanins, whose main compound is cyanidin-3-glucoside (Amaral, 2023). Different extraction methods exist, including more sophisticated ones; however, maceration in a low-boiling-point solvent, especially acidified water, shows better efficiency compared to ethanol (Santos, 2013).

The colorimetric behavior of the extract presents zones of trend inversion and color saturation regions at pH below 2.0 and above 9.0, as discussed by Amaral et al. (2023), which implies reduced hue variations at these extremes, a relevant aspect for quantitative color analysis.

2.2 Digital Color Measurements: RGB, HSV and Their Analytical Applications

Digital image recording constitutes a valuable resource for quantitative color analysis, being widely used as a fast and low-cost method. The RGB model is the most common standard, based on a three-dimensional cubic space that combines the three parameters. However, its representational capacity may be limited in some applications, given its dependence on the direct composition of channels (Effendhy, 2024).

In contrast, the HSV (Hue, Saturation, Value) space describes color through three components, more intuitive from the perspective of human perception: hue (0° to 360°), saturation (0 to 1), and value (0 to 1). The H parameter expresses the primary cognitive information of color and is widely used in the correlation between hue change and chemical transformation of substances for quantitative analysis purposes (Erenas, 2012). The cylindrical structure of the HSV space, with the distribution of H, S, and V, can be visualized in Figure 1.

Figure 1: (A) Cylindrical model highlighting the Hue, Saturation, and Value axes. (B) Interface of the application used to display the H, S, and V parameters from image capture.

Several studies have been exploring RGB, HSV, and other vector spaces for quantitative determination of substances, including correlation between hue and pH (Park, 2021) and groundwater analysis (Peeters, 2014). Effendhy et al. (2024) compared HSV, YCbCr, and YUV for pH determination using red cabbage extract, concluding that HSV showed the best performance in the employed method.

2.3 Machine Learning Applied to Colorimetric Analysis

Machine Learning is a set of mathematical methods developed over the last decades and widely disseminated since the 1990s, especially due to the facilitated access to languages and computational environments such as Python (Zhai, 2020). Although any method can be implemented from first principles, modern APIs offer a wide variety of algorithms, allowing direct application to different types of data.

Machine learning has already been applied to the analysis of contrasts between pH and color (Kim, 2021; Fairclough, 2020; Liu, 2019; Chioson, 2018; Kim, 2017; Moreno, 2012). In supervised methods, the data are divided into training and test sets, with a target variable responsible for the mathematical convergence of the model. In unsupervised methods, such as clustering, the algorithm operates without labels, using geometric and arithmetic metrics to determine natural groups in the data (Wulan Hastuti, 2020).

Classification methods can also be employed to separate distinct sectors in the data, while dimensionality reduction techniques explore mathematical relationships among variables to analyze multidimensional datasets, common in experimental science (Zhai, 2020). Ventura-Grandez (2025) used colorimetric parameters derived from red cabbage extract for substance identification, reinforcing the potential of digital analysis in this type of application.

In parallel, Wulan Hastuti et al. (2020) investigated the correlation between pH and the color of red cabbage extract using a professional digital camera, a fluorescent source, and a dark chamber; the data were acquired in RGB and converted to different vector spaces, being applied to classification methods and regression models, such as K-Nearest Neighbor (KNNR) and Artificial Neural Network (ANNR). The authors observed better RGB performance with the K-NN method.

3 METHODOLOGY

The study is of an experimental and instrumental nature, with a quantitative objective (Gil, 2002). The setup used consisted of a plastic piece designed to house a glass cuvette, an RGB LED (operated individually in red, green, and blue), and a smartphone with the Color mode available in the beta version of the Phyphox application (Figure 2).

The red cabbage extract was obtained by boiling 200.0 g of cabbage in 500.0 g of water. From this base extract, aliquots were adjusted to ten pH levels, using diluted alcohol vinegar for acidification and bleach (sodium hypochlorite 2.5%) for alkalization. The pH was measured with a pen-type meter, accuracy 0.01. Table 1 presents the volumetric planning employed.

Each sample was illuminated separately by each LED color, with three independent repetitions for each pH value. In each repetition, the original solution was discarded

Figure 2: Experimental scheme: photos of the kit.

Table 1: Dosage planning for the samples.

Sample	Extract (mL)	Additive volume (mL)	Additive
1	16.0	16.0	Vinegar
2	16.0	12.0	Vinegar
3	16.0	8.0	Vinegar
4	16.0	4.0	Water
5	16.0	4.0	Water
6	20.0	0.4	
7	20.0	0.8	
8	20.0	1.2	Sodium hypochlorite 2.5%
9	20.0	1.6	
10	20.0	2.0	

and a new aliquot was prepared, ensuring independence between collections. The color parameters Hue (H), Saturation (S), and Value (V) were obtained by Phyphox directly from the smartphone camera.

The procedure resulted in a dataset of 189 samples, structured in five features (pH, H, S, V, and LED color). The central hypothesis of the study is that one of the LED colors would produce better contrast in the color parameters, allowing the construction of a supervised model capable of estimating pH.

3.1 Cluster Analysis of Color Features

Clustering was applied separately to the sets obtained with each LED color. Three methods were used. The first, K-means, is a widely used partitional method due to its good accuracy and low computational cost (Rodriguez, 2019). The number of clusters was adjusted by the elbow method.

The second method is Agglomerative Clustering, which uses a hierarchical model based on the successive fusion of clusters according to distance matrices (Oti, 2024). It starts with each point as an individual cluster and performs iterative combinations until forming a single cluster, allowing the evaluation of the hierarchical structure of the data.

The third method was Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM). This method uses probabilistic modeling, assuming that the data come from a mixture of multivariate normal distributions (Patel, 2020). More flexible than K-means, it allows estimating likelihood and selecting the number of clusters via criteria such as AIC/BIC.

These methods were applied to verify whether the samples showed distinct patterns or overlap among themselves for each LED color, evaluating the consistency of the groupings.

3.2 Supervised Analysis Using Various Regression Methods

To estimate pH from the color parameters (H, S, and V), five regression methods were applied, analyzed separately for each LED color. The performance indicators used were R^2 , MAE (Mean Absolute Error), and MSE (Mean Squared Error), collected at their optimal adjustment values. The methods employed were:

- **Ridge Regression:** An L2 regularization model that reduces overfitting by penalizing the magnitude of the coefficients.
- **Linear Regression:** A parametric model based on ordinary least squares, used as a comparative reference (Filzmoser, 2021).
- **Support Vector Regression (SVR):** Applies the maximum margin principle to regression, using kernels to capture nonlinear relationships and robustness to outliers.

- **K-Nearest Neighbors Regression (KNNR):** Instance-based, predicts values by the mean of the k nearest neighbors in the feature space (Cunningham, 2021).
- **Random Forest Regression:** An ensemble method that aggregates multiple decision trees, reducing variance and increasing generalization (Grinsztajn, 2022).

The models were trained with the data obtained individually for each LED color, and subsequently compared regarding predictive performance.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The dataset was initially explored regarding the pairwise cross of the four numerical parameters. Figure 3 shows four graphs correlating the color parameters (H, S, and V) among themselves and the hue parameter (H) with the pH value. A segregation of the samples related to the green LED and a displacement of these samples in the Saturation \times Hue graph can be observed.

Figure 3: Pairwise cross between the color variables and pH value of each sample.

Another way to analyze this context of displaced samples is the correlation matrix in Figure 4. In the correlation matrix, a higher value means a greater degree of independence among the parameters regarding these characteristics. In particular, the pH values show a low value, which may indicate a tendency related to the other values, such as hue and saturation, limiting the independence of these parameters.

Figure 5 presents a 3D graph of the color parameters (A. Red, B. Green, and C. Blue) for each LED with the distribution of pH values in color scale. The samples related to the red and blue LEDs show a dispersed format in all directions and a random color

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Figure 4: Strength correlation between the variables.

scale tendency, which differs from the green LED values (Fig. 5B), which show a gradual distribution, suggesting an objective trend for precise data fitting.

Figure 5: Original data of color parameters and color scale of pH value for each LED: A) Red, B) Green, C) Blue.

4.1 Cluster Analysis

To evaluate the grouping structure present in the dataset, the analysis began with partitional methods, especially K-Means. As a first step, it was necessary to determine the appropriate number of clusters. Figure 6 presents the elbow curve and the variation of the

Silhouette Score as a function of the number of groups tested, allowing the identification of the best balance point between internal compactness and separation between clusters.

Figure 6: Elbow curve and Silhouette Score optimization.

The elbow curve should be analyzed by identifying the inflection point where the marginal reduction in the within-cluster sum of squares (WCSS) becomes negligible. Complementarily, the Silhouette Score (Rousseeuw, 1987) provides additional validation, with values close to 1 indicating well-defined clusters. Complementarily, the dendrogram, shown in Figure 7, allows visualization of the complete hierarchical structure of the data. The height of the mergers represents the dissimilarity between clusters, while the branching pattern reveals proximity relationships.

Figure 7: Dendrogram produced from the Agglomerative Clustering method.

Considering evaluation criteria such as the relative height of the mergers: low-height mergers indicate high similarity, while high-height mergers suggest distinctive clusters; the dendrogram structure: balanced dendrograms suggest clusters of similar sizes, while asymmetric structures may indicate the presence of outliers or clusters of variable density; and the cutting criterion: the ideal cutting point is located where the greatest increase in merger distance occurs (Müllner, 2011).

The clustering evaluation parameters are varied, highlighting: Silhouette Coefficient: between -1 and 1 , the higher the better; Calinski-Harabasz Index: the higher the better; Fowlkes-Mallows: similarity with K-means, $1 =$ perfect agreement; Homogeneity: each cluster contains only members of a single class; Completeness: all members of a class are in the same cluster; V-measure: harmonic mean between Homogeneity and Completeness; and Adjusted Rand Index: similarity between two clusterings.

Figure 8: Clustering result: A, B, C) optimization of Gaussian Mixture parameters, and D) 3D image of the clustered points.

The Silhouette Coefficient (SC) is the coefficient that measures how similar an object is to its own cluster compared to the other clusters: $SC > 0.7$: strong and well-defined clustering structure, $0.5 < SC \leq 0.7$: reasonable structure, $0.25 < SC \leq 0.5$: weak structure, possibility of artificial clusters, and $SC \leq 0.25$: no significant clustering structure. The Calinski-Harabasz (CH) index calculates the ratio between inter-cluster dispersion and intra-cluster dispersion, with higher values indicating better-defined clusters, particularly effective for data with spherical distribution. The Fowlkes-Mallows Score (FM) measures the similarity between two partitions, with $FM = 1$: perfect agreement, $FM = 0$: complete absence of agreement, intermediate values indicate degree of overlap. Finally, the Homogeneity, Completeness, and V-measure metrics evaluate different aspects of clustering quality. Homogeneity: each cluster contains only members of a single class; Completeness: all members of a given class are assigned to the same cluster; V-measure: harmonic mean between homogeneity and completeness; Adjusted Rand Index (ARI) corrects the Rand Index for chance, providing a more reliable measure of similarity between partitions.

Table 2: Best evaluation parameter values for each method.

Metric	K-Means	Agglomerative	Gaussian Mixture
Number of clusters (k)	4	4	4
Calinski-Harabasz Index	177.5953	172.7886	170.34
Silhouette Coefficient	0.5345	0.5250	0.5246
Fowlkes-Mallows Score	—	0.9478	0.9531
Homogeneity	—	0.9200	0.9162
Completeness	—	0.9200	0.9125
V-measure	—	0.9200	0.9144
Adjusted Rand Index	—	0.9259	0.9336

From the enormous diversity of existing mathematical tools in terms of unsupervised and supervised machine learning methodologies, some of these tools were employed for

performance comparison, since there is no single method with greater efficiency, always requiring comparison in scenarios, so that the main interest lies in the indices and parameters that show convergence among methods, strengthening the obtained conclusions.

4.2 Regression Analysis

Different performance evaluation parameters were employed. Figure 9 summarizes the values delivered by the evaluation of each of these parameters. In terms of dataset analysis, there is a very diversified computational potential where the most appropriate method must consider the characteristics of the dataset and comparative evaluation. Especially in the regression process, behaviors such as overfitting and underfitting need to be considered and analyzed, but given the complexity of the dataset itself, even a model with limitations inherent to the hyper-parameterization process demanded by each method already delivered, as a result, a numerically objective view of the dataset analysis.

The matrices in Figure 9A, 9B, and 9C summarize the performance parameters for each method applied to each LED. The quality of the R^2 score will be better the closer it is to 1, while the MAE and MSE values indicate better performance the smaller they are. In the case of the analyzed dataset, the five employed methods reinforced the prominence shown for the samples produced using the green LED light, with consistent results for all methods and for the three parameters used in this work.

Bringing a deeper look at the results obtained for the samples produced using the green LED, Figure 10 presents the main convergence of results for the method that showed the best performance indicators. The figure presents the predicted and real pH values in color scale. In part A of Figure 10, the 3D graph highlights in color scale the comparison between the real pH values and the predicted values, where minimal error can be observed. The method that presented the best fit performance was K-NN. Figure 10B shows the fit between predicted and real pH values. Despite outlier points, an adjustment with an R^2 Score of 0.89.

The use of machine learning methods offers high computational power for the analysis of multidimensional datasets; however, the quality of the results remains dependent on the adequate construction of the dataset and the experimental conditions that originate it. The algorithms used in this study represent only a fraction of the available approaches and belong to the group of methods with lower computational cost. Even so, the obtained results indicate that low-power, low-cost LED sources can be exploited in a more refined way in the characterization of substances, especially in color regions where individual emitters show differentiated performance.

The adoption of machine learning methods is a present reality, which increasingly occupies space, and spectroscopic techniques are essentially techniques that present a regular pattern and repetitive characteristics, which, although they have a highly qualified

A

B

C

Figure 9: Heatmap of performance parameters for each method and each LED category: A) R^2 score, B) MAE, and C) MSE.

Figure 10: A) Distribution of each sample by color parameters with two color scales: predicted pH and real pH; B) Adjustment curve predicted pH versus real pH.

view—that provided by the human mind—have the potential to show the visualization of micro details that would not go unnoticed mathematically in the statistical domain. Although the central objective of this work was the quantitative characterization of red cabbage extract under controlled illumination and its analysis by machine learning techniques, the proposed experimental setup shows potential for adaptation to educational environments. The availability of simple materials, such as RGB LED, plastic structure, and smartphone recording, favors its reproduction in Chemistry teaching activities, allowing discussion of limitations of natural indicators, influence of illumination conditions, and interpretation of experimental data. This didactic dimension, however, remains as a complementary possibility, not as the main purpose of the investigation.

5 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The study presented an accessible experimental strategy for the quantitative analysis of the colorimetric response of red cabbage extract under different pH levels and controlled illumination conditions. The combination of a low-cost setup, composed of an RGB LED, cuvette, and smartphone recording, with the application of clustering and regression methods allowed a systematic evaluation of how the choice of light source influences the distribution of color parameters in HSV space. The results showed that green illumination produces the most consistent separation among samples and enables the training of a supervised model with robust performance, even in the face of the chemical limitations associated with the use of bleach as an alkalizing agent.

These findings reinforce the utility of the proposed methodology for quantitative studies involving natural indicators, highlighting the importance of standardizing illumination and the care in choosing reagents that may introduce interferences unrelated to pH. The machine learning-based approach proved effective in exploring patterns in the data and obtaining predictive models with good generalization.

In summary, while one can manually observe a certain tendency when using the green

LED for the measured color changes, the application of different unsupervised machine learning methodologies indicated a clear mathematical stratification when relating color as a function of the acidity and alkalinity level of the sample. By analogy, the presented results contribute so that segmentation of this type of spectroscopy advances in methodologies based on computational processing that requires little investment.

Although not the central focus of the work, the simplicity of the experimental apparatus and the use of widely available instruments suggest that the methodology can be adapted to educational contexts, contributing to activities that integrate experimentation, data analysis, and critical discussion of methodological limitations. Future developments include the evaluation of other light sources, comparison with different natural indicators, and expansion of the dataset to improve predictive models.

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